

METHODS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY

Hudayberdiyev Nodirbek Abdullayevich
Tashkent Oriental University, dean
of the faculty of physical education

Abstract: The article analyzes how to organize physical education activities in preschool educational organizations, the formation of physical skills and competencies of children from an early age, and the issues of proper implementation of physical education of children in the family.

Key words: preschool educational organizations, children, children's physical education, physical skills and competencies, morning gymnastics, action games.

INTRODUCTION

Development and growth of preschool children are a continuous process. In this period, the proper organization of children's physical education, the formation of physical skills and competencies from an early age, and the comprehensive development of them are the main requirements of the theory of physical education in preschool education. Today's children, regardless of where they live, they constantly have to face changes in social, political, ecological, scientific, technical and industrial spheres. The development and growth of a child is a continuous process. During this period, we observe his formation as a person, his first attempt to understand the world through the objects and objects around him and find meaning from it, his interests, feelings, and physical development. Each period of life has its own stages according to developmental characteristics and needs. Pre-school period can be included in the child's growth and development.

Children are a melodious universe and live in a world of rapid growth, development and change. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 5, 2018 No. 5368 "On measures to fundamentally improve the state management system in the field of physical education and sports", the priority of educational institutions in the field of mass sports development and selection of talented young people directions are defined, and it is determined to form interest in physical education and sports training in children for physical development and strengthening of health by conducting classes on elementary gymnastics and movement games in preschool educational organizations. Decision No. PQ-5282 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 5, 2021, pre-school education aims to form a healthy and mature, physical development of a child's personality, while preparing for school. In the process of physical education conducted under the guidance of a teacher, the child acquires movement skills and skills based on the requirements of each age group. The change of various types of movement during the study will add to the education of the child's physical qualities. Level of development of physical qualities and determines the success of children's movement activities and teaches them to acquire new forms of movement and use them appropriately in life. Movement skill is repeated in the theory of physical education as the level of mastery of movement technique. It involves excessive focusing of attention on one point and the use of unstable methods in performing a movement task.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The tasks of raising children physically in the family and in state institutions are a whole process, and these tasks are solved by the joint efforts of parents and employees of preschool educational institutions.

In the family, from a young age, the child is taught the skills of performing complex movements, for example, riding a bicycle, swimming in water, and other similar movements. Mastering the types of physical exercises to help the child

individually and be careful during the exercise it is necessary to provide a measure. It is much more difficult to teach children with such exercises in preschool institutions than to teach them at home.

In order to properly implement physical education in the family, parents should know what kind of physical exercises children are doing in preschool educational institutions. Parents should also know what kind of physical activity their children are doing in the sports school during the whole day and during the whole week. Taking into account all these burdens, a plan of training will be made with the child after he returns home from kindergarten. In the same way, morning gymnastics, active games, etc. are planned and practiced for weekends and holidays. Parents whose children do not go to kindergarten should take care of their full physical development. All the means of physical education in the family as well as in pre-school educational organizations use in a complex manner is of great importance. Creating favorable hygienic conditions, natural factors in the environment (water, sun, air) It is very important to use, perform various physical exercises; that children engage in all types of physical labor that they can, perform all actions correctly, various types of activities (painting, making various shapes from plasticine and clay) should be followed. Physical exercise in the family is carried out in various forms: morning physical education, training, active games, exercise treatments, walks and others are included. In this area, parents work together with their children and set an example for them, for example, if they play badminton and tennis together, get into the water together with the children, swim with them, etc. if they hold similar events in cooperation, it will have a positive effect on the education of preschool children. Parents teach children about physical education, teach them how to do physical exercises correctly. In this way, a particularly favorable psychological climate is created for raising children and strengthening their health.

CONCLUSION

In the process of physical training, parents monitor the mood of children and coordinate physical loads. Two or three times a year, it is recommended to monitor the child's health, physical development and physical fitness indicators, mainly in the chapter "Planning and accounting of physical education work in preschool education institutions". This information will help parents to analyze the work done on physical education and make a plan for the next period. Employees of pre-school education institutions should closely assist parents in this work.

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